

METHODOLOGY FOR ORGANIZING PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE- TESTING WORK ON DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE ENGINEER-ENERGY PERSONNEL

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Abstract: The aim of this article is to improve the methodology for developing professional competence of future energy engineers with the help of a developed training manual and electronic textbooks. In this article, experimental work was conducted on students of the energy engineering department, selecting three higher educational institutions as the object of research.

Keywords: competence, energy engineering, electrical engineering, power supply, individual, innovation, didactic opportunity.

Software tools have been developed for organizing experimental training sessions for future power engineering personnel in the specialty subjects "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises" using innovative and interactive methods. Experimental training sessions were carried out on the basis of this software tool, and problems that need to be solved in experimental training were identified.

Problems that need to be solved in experimental training sessions:

The lack of integration of the teaching of the subjects "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Electrical Supply of Industrial Enterprises" with the disciplines of the specialty and the organizational concept that meets the requirements of the time;

- the lack of improvement in the model for organizing the training of specialists and implementing the educational process;

- the lack of improvement in the methodology for teaching subjects related to the specialty when conducting lectures, practical and experimental training for future energy engineers;

- the lack of close connection between the processes of theoretical knowledge, practical training and experimental work with disciplines related to the specialty using dual educational technologies;

- the purpose of the pilot study was to develop scientifically based methodological recommendations based on the specific results obtained in the teaching and implementation of disciplines related to the specialty in higher educational institutions using software tools.

The following tasks were determined for the experimental work carried out in higher educational institutions:

1. To form innovative projects of lessons in the subjects "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises" in technical higher educational institutions of engineering and power engineering specialties, to study the state of teaching.

2. To determine the place of the innovative model in the subject in improving teaching methods in the current lessons.

3. To determine experimental and control groups in the lesson.

4. To draw up projects for lectures, practical and experimental lessons, to improve and pilot-test the teaching methods of subjects related to the specialty.

5. To pilot-test the recommended and developed educational and methodological works and didactic materials.

6. To determine the effectiveness of the proposed methodology in teaching subjects related to the specialty using mathematical and statistical methods.

7. To determine the stages of conducting experimental work on the use of modern interactive methods of teaching:

- 8.1. Preparatory stage - at this stage, the control and experimental groups for the experimental test are determined, the general state of organization and conduct of training is studied, the state of design and teaching of training courses in the subjects "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Power Supply of

Industrial Enterprises" is studied, and questionnaire questions are developed. This process is carried out in the form of collecting data, observing the process and conducting interviews.

8.2. Research stage - to carry out experimental work on the quality teaching of the subjects "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Electricity Supply of Industrial Enterprises" developed at this stage using modern interactive methods, to effectively convey the content of the subjects to students in a qualitative form through the recommended and improved existing didactic and educational-methodical resources, and at the same time to provide methodological assistance to teachers in the field based on the development of educational activities based on pedagogical and information technologies in the research process.

8.3. Teaching stage - during the experimental work, it was planned to organize the work in the experimental group using the textbook "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and the electronic textbook "Electricity Supply of Industrial Enterprises" and educational literature based on innovative pedagogical and information technologies.

Conduct training for future engineering and energy personnel based on the experience of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions based on the existing educational literature in the control group.

8.4. Confirmatory stage - finalizing and summarizing the conducted experimental work. Developing topics based on questionnaires, tests, questionnaires, interviews, increasing topics as necessary, distributing them to teachers and students. Developing a project of conducted experimental training, lesson plans, teaching methodical recommendations, participating as a direct participant in the training processes. Providing recommendations to the control and experimental groups on the conduct of designed training sessions.

9. Analysis of the educational and methodological materials prepared for the organization of classes in the subject "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" in higher educational institutions of the technical direction based on the software educational tools of the subject "Electrical Supply of Industrial Enterprises" and the results obtained.

10. Mathematical and statistical reworking of the results obtained during the conducted experimental and test work.

11. Drawing conclusions based on the comparative analysis of the results obtained at the end of the experimental and test work.

When conducting experimental and test work, the following methods were used: pedagogical experience; pedagogical observation; conducting

questionnaire surveys, interviews and test results. Experimental and test work on scientific research was carried out in selected technical higher educational institutions based on the developed program. Interviews were held with students during experimental and test work, tests were organized, and questionnaires were distributed. In order to organize pilot projects based on these pilot programs, first of all, opinions were exchanged with the leadership and teaching staff of technical higher education institutions, and the results obtained were analyzed.

The research process in technical higher education institutions is aimed at further improving the quality of the educational process by teaching students studying in the "Power Engineering" field of study in the subjects of "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises" using innovative and interactive methods, and improving the methodology for using them in production processes. Based on this perspective, experimental work was conducted in three stages in three technical higher education institutions of our Republic, namely in the field of study 60710400-Power Engineering of Bukhara State Technical University (BDTU), Navoi State University of Mining and Technology (NDKTU) and Karshi State Technical University (QDTU) (see Table 1).

Table 1**The number of students from three higher educational institutions of our Republic participated in the experiment**

T/r	Higher education institution	Students who participated
1	Bukhara State Technical University	274
2	Navoi State University of Mining and Technology	442
3	Karshi State Technical University	290
	Total:	1006

The first preparatory stage of the pilot study conducted in the 2024-2025 academic year was carried out, during which the control and experimental groups of the selected higher educational institutions were determined. The general situation of conducting and organizing the training sessions was designed, and questionnaire questions were developed. As a result of these analyses, results were obtained through the methods of collecting data, observation and conducting interviews.

The results and materials obtained in the pilot study were collected in the following order, based on the goals and objectives of the scientific research work:

The curriculum, subject programs, educational standards, content of textbooks and textbooks of the "Power Engineering" educational direction were studied;

In the "Power Engineering" educational direction, experimental groups were identified from students for teaching the subjects "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises" and "Electrical Materials. Installation of Electrical Equipment";

After conducting lectures, practical and experimental training sessions on the experimental testing of the prepared educational materials on the subjects of "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises", using innovative developments of lessons based on interactive methods developed at the end of the first and second stages of the experimental testing work, the achievements and shortcomings of teaching were identified, general conclusions were drawn on the improvement of the above teaching methodology, and the following recommendations were made based on the established recommendations:

The levels of mastery of the selected experimental and control groups of students in higher technical educational institutions, determined on the basis of control work, questions and answers, and which are effective in developing the professional competencies of future engineering and power engineering personnel, were compared based on comparative analyses and conclusions were drawn;

The innovative lesson development projects of the lessons conducted with the "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" textbook and the electronic textbook "Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises" developed as a result of the experiment were improved in content based on recommendations and conclusions;

a general analysis of the conducted experimental work was developed.

In the above two stages, final experimental work was carried out on the current real state of the experimental work, and the materials of the experimental work were collected and analyzed. The experimental results were summarized, general conclusions were formulated, and processed using mathematical and statistical methods.

The third - this training stage of the experimental work was held in the 2025-2026 academic years. In the experimental groups, lessons were conducted based on the "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" textbook and the electronic textbook

“Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises”. In the control groups, the experiments were conducted based on the current educational literature and the pedagogical experience of professors and teachers of the higher educational institution.

After eliminating the identified shortcomings of the methodology for teaching the subjects "Theoretical Electrical Engineering" and "Power Supply of Industrial Enterprises", collected at the second, that is, research stage, the reliability of the recommended improved methodology was checked.

The conducted experimental work was completed and conclusions were drawn. Samples of questionnaires, tests, questionnaires were increased in the amount corresponding to the number of students in the experimental and control groups.

A project for conducting experimental training sessions, lesson plans, and teaching methodical recommendations were developed. Based on direct participation in the research and observations, recommendations were made on conducting the designed training sessions in the control and experimental groups.

In the technical higher educational institutions where the experiments were conducted, training sessions were organized on this subject and the results obtained were summarized. The results obtained in the experimental and test works were processed mathematically and statistically, and at the end of the experiment, a general conclusion was drawn based on the comparison of the indicators of the experimental and test works.

At the end of the third stage, tests and written works were administered to the experimental groups where the experiments were conducted. In order to assess the knowledge of students, to draw up lesson plans and projects, and to demonstrate the effectiveness of applying the improved methodology to the educational process, a 100-point assessment system was used to facilitate the calculation of the results of the interviews, tests and control works conducted in the experimental and control groups with high accuracy.

At the beginning of the pilot study of students studying at technical higher educational institutions, the results of 503 participants in the control group and 503 participants in the experimental group were analyzed based on the criterion of closeness of mastery indicators (see Table 2).

Table 2

The number of students who participated in experimental work

Groups	Total number of students	Academic years		
		2023-2024	2024-2025	2025-2026
Experience	503	151	189	163
Control	503	148	174	181
Total	1006	299	363	344

Based on the general theory of the research work, it was proven to be effective in the process of implementing pilot projects to improve the methodology for developing the professional competencies of future engineering and power engineering personnel. Discussions were held with the participation of management staff and professors of higher technical educational institutions where the pilot projects were carried out, and appropriate conclusions were drawn, taking into account the suggestions, recommendations and comments provided.

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